

ENHANCING THE PROPERTIES OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES WITH VERTICALLY ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBES INTERLEAVES

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ABSTRACT

The incorporation of vertically aligned carbon nanotubes (VACNT) at the interply region of laminated structures has demonstrated significant reinforcement of carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) composite materials [1]. This reinforcement mechanism results from the deflection of micro-cracks towards strong intralaminar regions instead of their propagation along weak interlaminar ones [2], thus reducing delamination. Furthermore, VACNT interplies have been shown to enhance the thermal, electrical, and gas impermeability properties of structural composites, thereby opening more opportunities to benefit from multifunctionalities [3].

Traditionally, the integration of such a reinforcing nanoengineered layer at the interface between plies involves the direct transfer of the VACNT layer from its original substrate (utilized during the synthesis process via catalytic CVD [4]) onto the surface of a carbon fiber ply pre-impregnated with resin (Figure 1a), the subsequent steps of the composite manufacturing process remaining unchanged. However, despite the simplicity and straightforwardness of this approach, it suffers from limitations in terms of cost-efficiency, scalability and carbon footprint for practical deployment at large scale.

A more industrially viable solution would involve the development of a VACNT supporting film (Figure 1b) that would be fully integrable into the final CFRP structure as an interleave. This methodology would significantly facilitate the commercial distribution and seamless integration of VACNT into existing manufacturing processes of advanced laminated composite parts.

In this study, we report recent progress towards developing such a nanoengineered interleave.

1 INTRODUCTION

In today's competitive engineering landscape, industries like aerospace, energy, infrastructure and sporting goods increasingly rely on composite materials to meet stringent design requirements. These applications demand materials that are lightweight, strong, cost-effective and easy to manufacture. A notable innovation is the integration of VACNT in between plies of laminated composites, commercially available and known as NAWAH Stitch.

NAWAH Stitch is a cutting-edge 3D nanocarbon interface for laminated composites materials. It provides enhanced mechanical, electrical and thermal properties to fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) without altering the part design and manufacturing process. Incorporating NAWAH Stitch between composite layers (Figure 1) improves toughness and impact resistance, reduces delamination and prolongs service life. Additionally, the use of NAWAH Stitch allows composite parts to be functionalized for advanced applications such as de-icing, in-situ matrix curing and structural health monitoring [5].

Figure 1 SEM of VACNT inserted between two carbon fiber composite plies

NAWAH is a global manufacturer of VACNT that produces this material at industrial scale on flexible metal sheets in a roll-to-roll fashion (Figure 2). This is done through a continuous atmospheric pressure chemical vapour deposition (APCVD) process at two production sites located in Rousset (France) and Dayton, Ohio (USA).

Figure 2 Vertically Aligned Carbon Nanotube synthesized by APCVD Roll-to-Roll process at NAWAH (left – post-synthesis optic visualisation and right – SEM VACNT on metallic support)

2 STATE OF THE ART

The added values of integrating VACNT at interplies have already been demonstrated by many previous studies [6,7]. These demonstrations always involved a direct transfer of VACNT onto the surface of prepreg plies. This approach (Figure 3), although efficient, suffers from several drawbacks that hinder their industrial scale deployment and adoption by the composite industry including:

- high logistics cost and CO2 footprint,
- reduced prepreg shelf lifetime.

This is mainly because thermosetting resins like epoxy must be stored at low temperature and have a limited shelf lifetime.

Figure 3 Standard process flow for integration of NAWAH Stitch

Therefore, a new method allowing for room temperature storage and easy handling would be highly advantageous. We report here below such a method.

3 NEW RESULTS

Thermoplastic (TP) polymers are stable at room temperature and some of them are miscible in epoxy resins [8]. Several epoxy-miscible thermoplastic films have thus been tested as support film for VACNT with the aim of:

- allowing for efficient transfer of VACNT from their original growth substrate,
- minimizing the weight and volume increase of the composite part due to the addition of the thermoplastic film as an interleave between prepreg plies,
- ensuring good compatibility with epoxy systems by avoiding any alteration of the original properties,
- retaining the beneficial properties of the inserted VACNT by providing a direct bridging of the fibers of adjacent plies by the carbon nanotubes,
- providing a low cost, scalable and stable at room temperature solution
- allowing for an easy handling and utilisation by the customer as an interleave in his composite manufacturing process.

The VACNT integration process with this method is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4 NAWAH's interleave method: integration via interleaving an epoxy-miscible thermoplastic polymer film supporting the VACNT

Several thermoplastic polymers have successfully been used to practically implement this new method. As an illustration, Figure 5 shows a reference roll of VACNT directly transferred on a prepreg and an example of a roll of VACNT transferred on a thin (typically 1 μm thick) thermoplastic film.

Figure 5 a) Roll of VACNT layer directly transferred on carbon fiber ply pre-impregnated with resin, b) Roll of VACNT layer transferred on thin thermoplastic film (both with SEM image inserts).

To demonstrate that all requirements specified above are met, reference composite panels have been prepared without NAWAH Stitch (Baseline) and compared with similar parts integrating NAWAH Stitch with the interleave method.

For this comparison, the selected prepreg system and layup was the HexPly® 8552S/37%/AGP280/C woven system from Hexcel with a $[0]_{12}$ layup. The panels were assembled and cured in autoclave according to the specifications of the prepreg manufacturer with the only difference for the NAWAH Stitched panel being the insertion of a TP film supported VACNT interleave between every prepreg ply. The thickness of the two cured panels were measured and the difference was found to be insignificant (lower than 5%).

A morphology comparison of the resin-rich interply regions was captured by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) cross sections (Fig. 6). It confirms that the interply thickness (between yellow arrows on Figure 6) remains unchanged with or without NAWAH Stitch (typically 10-15 μ m). In particular, the VACNT supporting thermoplastic film is no longer visible after curing, thus confirming its dissolution into the epoxy matrix. As targeted, the VACNT layer bridges the carbon fibers from adjacent plies, this configuration being the most favorable to achieve enhanced mechanical properties.

Figure 6 a) SEM Cross-section of baseline CFRP , b) SEM Cross-section of CFRP with integrated NAWAH Stitch interleave

4 CONCLUSIONS

VACNT layers inserted between plies of laminated composites, commercially available and known as NAWAH Stitch, have long proven their advantages but the adoption of this technology by the composite industry has been limited so far by the classical method for transferring them directly on prepreg surface. A new method involving the transfer of VACNT on an epoxy-miscible thermoplastic film and the subsequent use of this film as an interleave in the composite manufacturing process was reported. The successful bridging of fibers from adjacent plies in a laminated epoxy-based CFRP composite was demonstrated by using this new method, without measurable increase of thickness.

Further steps at NAWAH include static mechanical testing for strength under short-beam shear (SBS) interlaminar shear stress (ILSS) and fatigue life testing under 3-points bending cycles. Besides, efforts continue towards full roll-to-roll scale up of this technology at the level of VACNT synthesis, thermoplastic film production and VACNT transfer on this film.

These results pave the way for lower cost, lower CO₂ footprint, easier processability and wider adoption of VACNT technology by the composite industry.

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